

Oxy-fuel with low NO_x despite high nitrogen presence in aluminium and steel industry

Martin Demuth, Andrew Richardson, Stefan Schwarz, Christian Kislinger @TOTeM 27.5.2026

NOx emissions normalized

<- Oxy-fuel | Air-fuel ->

1250
20
1%
2,85%
1,015

Furnace temp
Oxidizer preheat
O₂% off-gas wet based
O₂% off-gas dry based
Lambda

1250
450
1%
1,23%
1,056

NOx emissions normalized

<- Oxy-fuel | Air-fuel ->

1250
20
1%
2,85%
1,015
1/3 OF off-gas (33%)
~1/11 AF off-gas (~10%)

Furnace temp
Oxidizer preheat
O ₂ % off-gas wet based
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Lambda
Dry ppm NOx measurement in

1250
450
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~9/11 AF off-gas (~81%)

NOx emissions normalized

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Furnace temp
Oxidizer preheat
O₂% off-gas wet based
O₂% off-gas dry based
Lambda
Dry ppm NO_x measurement in

Recalculation (EN 267)
with O₂-compensation:

From
ppm | mg/Nm³ @3%O₂
to
mg/kWh @3%O₂

1250
450
1%
1,23%
1,056
~9/11 AF off-gas (~81%)

NOx “Magna Charta”

<- Oxy-fuel | Air-fuel ->

Example product	Burner, flame	Impulse	Staging	NOx-	Emis.	NOx-	Emis.	Burner, flame	Impulse	Staging	Example product
Messer				low	high	high	low				
Oxipyr family				ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm				
P	Pipe-in-pipe, orange flame			2000	3000	XXX	200	80ies, burn, baby, burn			
						150	100	Optimized swirl disk	Optim. mixing		KS flame mode
PLon	p-in-p, soft orange flame	Low turbul.		500	1500	60	40	Multiple injections	High	Yes	KS menox® +
F	p-in-p, blue flame	High		200	300	30	20	Flameless	High	Yes, multi	KS menox® - Tenova TSX
SplitOx	semi-flameless	High	Yes	100	150		<10	Radiant tube (<1000 °C)	Single power	Yes	WS single digit
SplitOx V2 LEAF	flameless	Very High	Yes	20	30						

NOx “Magna Charta”

<- Oxy-fuel Air-fuel ->

Example product	Burner, flame	Impulse	Staging	NOx- Emis.	NOx- Emis.	Burner, flame	Impulse	Staging	Example product		
Messer				low	low	low	low				
Oxipyr family				ppm	mg/kWh	mg/kWh	ppm				
P	Pipe-in-pipe, orange flame			2000	420	380	200				
						190	100	Optimized swirl disk	Optim. mixing	KS flame mode	
PLon	p-in-p, soft orange flame	Low turbul.		500	105	80	40	Multiple injections	High	Yes	KS menox® +
F	p-in-p, blue flame	High		200	40	40	20	Flameless	High	Yes, multi	KS menox® - Tenova TSX
SplitOx	semi-flameless	High	Yes	100	20	<20	<10	Radiant tube (<1000 °C)	Single power	Yes	WS single digit
SplitOx V2 LEAF	flameless	Very High	Yes	20	4						

Oxipyr-F, pipe-in-pipe, high impulse, 200 ppm NOx base

OF non-staged with N₂

<- Oxy-fuel Air-fuel ->

Example product	Burner, flame	Impulse	Staging	NOx- Emis.	NOx- Emis.	NOx- Emis.	NOx- Emis.	Burner, flame	Impulse	Staging	Example product
Messer				low	low	low	low				
Oxipyr family				ppm	mg/kWh	mg/kWh	ppm				
P	Pipe-in-pipe, orange flame	<div style="border: 2px solid green; padding: 5px; text-align: center;"> Non-staging oxy-fuel burners are VERY N₂-sensitive </div>		2000	420	380	200	80ies, burn, baby, burn			
						190	100	Optimized swirl disk	Optim. mixing		KS flame mode
PLon	p-in-p, soft orange flame	Low turbul.		500	105	80	40	Multiple injections	High	Yes	KS menox® +
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Bloom Reheating Furnace

Co-funded by
the European Union

MESSER
Gases for Life

Oxipyr-SplitOx V2 and Air-fuel

Co-funded by
the European Union

AF & non-staged OF

900 mg/kWh

<- Oxy-fuel Air-fuel ->

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SplitOx V2 LEAF	flameless	Very High	Yes	20	4						

AF & staged OF

<- Oxy-fuel Air-fuel ->

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2x Oxipyr-SplitOx V2 in BRF

Co-funded by
the European Union

Air-fuel

Oxy-fuel + air-fuel

2x Oxipyr-SplitOx V2 in BRF

Co-funded by
the European Union

Air-fuel

Zone 3

Oxy-fuel + air-fuel

Zone 3

Oxygen ?vs? air

<- Oxy-fuel | Air-fuel ->

Up to 40% Faster Melting
Oxygen supply
Higher Efficiency
Reduced CO₂ Emissions
High gas radiation (H₂O, CO₂)
Heat Transfer >700 °C
Sensitive to furnace pressure / false air

Established Technology
Low Operating Cost
Need for Energy Recovery
High Momentum
High Convection
Heat Transfer <700 °C
High Furnace Pressure

Tailor Oxygen Use to Meet Process Needs

Holding:	Oxygen ↓	Air ↑
Melting:	Oxygen ↑	Air ↓

Oxipyr-LEAF Burner Technology

Separate jet technology:

- Air and/or Oxygen
- Flame and flameless

Distributed reaction

- Temperature uniformity
- Flameless avoids hot flame regions
- Very low NOx emissions

3D-Printed temperature and corrosion resistant nozzles

- Outer air-shrouded high velocity oxygen injectors
- Central Natural Gas Injector (with air and oxygen for 'flame' mode)
- Avoids failure points from machining/welds

NOx vs Oxygen Concentration

Oxipyr-LEAF Field Results

Goal: Reduce energy consumption by 20% on existing oxy-fuel Aluminum remelting furnace (hearth)

- With California Energy Commission and GTI Energy

CALIFORNIA ENERGY COMMISSION

GTI ENERGY

Fuel and Oxygen Savings vs Charge Rate Savings with LEAF over Oxy-fuel Baseline

3 years of operation – independent results validation:

- Savings: Natural Gas >24% and Oxygen >37%
- 60% lower maximum firing rate
 - Reduced furnace temperatures & improved yield
- Passed current and future SCAQMD NOx limits
- Zero degradation on burner parts

Oxygen + air combustion ... can be done right

TOTeM 52 – Oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS

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